

CASPAR PAYLOAD ADAPTER STRUCTURAL FAILURE TEST RESULTS AND ANALYTICAL PREDICTIONS

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SUMMARY

The CASPAR payload adapter was tested to structural failure at the Air Force Research Laboratory as part of a larger program intended to determine the ultimate capacity of three large composite structures and to evaluate failure analysis methods. This paper discusses the failure test design and results with comparison to analytical predictions.

Keywords: composites, failure, static testing, model correlation, aerospace structures

INTRODUCTION

The Air Force Research Laboratory (AFRL) Space Vehicles Directorate conducted structural failure static tests on large space composite structures. The work was performed by CSA Engineering and utilized three, previously flight-qualified, developmental, launch vehicle components. The three test articles were: 1) the Composite Adapter for Shared PAYload Rides (CASPAR) payload adapter, 2) an Atlas V Conical interstage adapter, and 3) a Delta IV 1780 payload attach fitting. The objective of this investigation is to quantitatively demonstrate the ultimate structural capability of the components, to compare the values to the flight conditions, and to analytically generated failure predictions. The desire is to evaluate the validity of the various material strength allowable criterion and finite element methods commonly used in the aerospace industry. In this paper, the experimental results for CASPAR, the program's first test article, are compared to industry standard finite element analysis failure predictions.

CASPAR is a payload adapter designed to support two co-manifested 1500 pound primary payloads, or up to four smaller spacecraft with an adapter. The dual payload adapter, shown in Figure 1, consists of two symmetrical shells that are 74 inches in diameter which tapers to a standard 62.01 inch bolt pattern on integrated composite flanges. The overall height of the adapter is 60 inches. The monocoque shells are constructed from IM7/8552 carbon fiber/toughened epoxy composite material. Each shell contains an access door and four evenly spaced vent holes on the conical region. Operationally, one of the satellites is placed atop the adapter, while the other is stowed inside. To deploy the stowed satellite, the adapter must release its upper half. To achieve this, Planetary Systems Corporation further developed their low shock Latching Lightband (LLB) separation system for integration into the mid-plane of CASPAR. The LLB is bonded to the shells with no mechanical fasteners.¹ Due to cost and schedule constraints of the CASPAR development program, a stiffness simulator was

incorporated in the qualification unit that consisted of flight unit aluminum extrusions with the same bonded interface to the composite, however, the latching mechanism was replaced with bolts that emulated the stiffness of the full system. These bolts connected CASPAR's two halves but did not fasten the separation system to the composite shells. The details of this design are thoroughly discussed in Maly². The aforementioned composite flanges, door cut-outs, vent holes, and bonded joints created difficult geometric discontinuities that were the focus of the failure analyses and test.

Figure 1. The CASPAR Payload Adapter Design Features

EXPERIMENTAL CONSIDERATIONS

The primary objectives of the overall failure test program and this experiment were: 1) produce flight-like composite failure in the test article; 2) acquire sufficient data to correlate the test results to the finite element predictions; and 3) identify the failure mechanisms and their sequence. The failure test program is detailed in Sanford³. The test configuration was designed to accomplish these goals which required balancing factors such as the interface hardware stiffnesses, the discrete load locations, and the magnitudes of each applied force. Additionally, strain, displacement, and video locations were positioned to capture the test events.

Figure 2. CASPAR Failure Test Setup

Qualification test analyses and data determined the best location to achieve a flight-like composite failure in CASPAR was in the aft conical region and its transition to the integrated composite flange at the 270° azimuth, located opposite the access door cut-out and 90° from either motor assembly discontinuity in the Lightband system. This location was chosen because the bond between the access door doublers and the structural shells was predicted to fail under compressive loading before the overall structure, which in turn causes the unsupported door cut-outs to buckle, resulting in structural failure. Likewise the LLB motor assembly cut-out introduces a discontinuity in the bonded joint, shown in Figure 1. These critical regions of the structural system were demonstrated during the qualification process but required sheltering from catastrophic test loads to meet the test objective of a relevant structural composite failure. The final constraint was to preserve the forward stiffness adapter because the adapter is crucial test hardware used in many developmental test efforts. To focus the maximum compressive load at one azimuth, a bending moment was integrated into the test design. Additional axial compressive force was required, however, to reach critical stress levels in the desired region while reducing the net tension load experienced by the access doors. The magnitude of the final applied axial load was limited to prevent yielding of the forward adapter. The failure test setup, shown in Figure 2, contained three actuators, simultaneously applying load to achieve the desired stress state in the aft composite transition region of CASPAR. The two vertical 100 kip jacks were used to apply a pure compressive load while the lateral 44 kip actuator induced bending and shear into the structure. The axial-to-bending load ratio was delicately balanced to observe the configuration's limitations while maximizing the compressive force in the critical composite region. The three load lines concurrently applied the load according to the profile shown in Figure 3.

Figure 3. CASPAR Failure Test Load Profile

The profile specified four load ramps. The first increased load to 50 percent of the flight, or limit, line load. The run was used to verify the instrumentation was functioning and recording properly. Next, the structure was exposed to the flight, 100 percent flight load condition to validate its integrity before proceeding to potentially catastrophic levels. The third run ramped up to 250 percent to capture data that corresponded to one percent load increments up until the level where the potentially damaging events, discussed in the next section, were predicted to begin. The final cycle

was set for 884 percent of the limit load, a level limited by the max force the lateral actuator could apply. Based on the predictions, structural failure would be achieved before the profile met its target point.

The same instrumentation suite used in the qualification was utilized for the failure test with two exceptions. The four rosette gages located on the aft stiffness adapter were discarded with the removal of the adapter from test stack, as discussed in Sanford³. Additionally two rosettes were added to the forward adapter to monitor the peak compressive and tensile strains. In all 33 uni-axial strain gages and 20 strain gage rosettes, a total of 93 strain channels, were recorded during the failure test. In addition, six displacement transducers were mounted to measure the axial displacements of the forward and aft flanges. These data were used to compare the predicted events to realized experimental incidents.

ANALYTICAL OVERVIEW

Third-party finite element modelling specialists were retained to predict the failure mechanisms and sequences for this experiment. A consultant from ATK Space Systems in San Diego, CA was hired to apply aerospace industry standard modelling practices using FEMAP pre/post-processor and the NASTRAN solver to generate the structural model. Firehole Technologies used Helius:MCT⁴ to evaluate the failure experiment. Their efforts are documented in Nelson⁵. This paper analyzes the events predicted by the industry-standard approach by identifying when each occurred as a percent of the flight load and providing the supporting data that indicated each incident. Table 1 lists the potential failure mechanisms in order of their analytical occurrence. Ultimately the analysis indicated aft joint compression as the cause of structural failure.

Table 1. Predicted Failure Events

Demonstrated Level (% Limit Load)	Predicted Level (% Limit Load)	Event Description
	253	Separation System Gapping
	283	Access Door Doubler Bond Failure
	370	Sep System Bolt Yielding in-line with Access Door
	400	Separation System Extrusion Yielding
	465	Aft Joint Composite Tension
	600	Aft Joint Composite Compression
	620	Open Hole Tension Failure at Aft Vent Hole
	646	Open Hole Compression Failure at Aft Vent Hole
	846	Shell Buckling

Previously, an analysis of the qualification test stack was performed with a finite element model and compared with a partial model of the Minotaur IV Launch Vehicle stack including CASPAR. Analysis results were the foundation for assessing what could be achieved during testing, including limitations of candidate test configurations. Once the qualification test configuration was approved, a second model was constructed to represent the final test configuration. With that detail previously documented, this program discarded the launch vehicle comparison and used only the qualification test FEM to validate the failure test configuration.

The failure test modeling efforts are shown in Figure 4. The first finite element model constructed was the global representation in which CASPAR, its Lightband, and the forward stiffness adapter were modeled using shell elements. The access-door doublers were included in the model, but the non-structural access covers were not. The load

head and test loads were idealized as a point mass, connected to the forward adapter with rigid elements, on the load head's axis of rotation at the elevation where the lateral load was applied. One axial and one lateral load were imparted on the point to apply the test loads to the structure. The base of the test article was fixed for this analysis. The key areas of the structure were the access door doubler bond, the Lightband separation system extrusion and bonded joint, the aft bolted interface, and the composite transition regions. These areas were investigated in detail with the FEM. The results of the shell analysis, also shown in Figure 4, concluded the compression of the aft joint would cause structural failure. A refined regional solid model was then developed to better represent the aft boundary condition and to improve the failure prediction. Shown in Figure 4, the solid model was created to specifically capture interlaminar stress in the composite in the transition radii from the conic region to the aft flange. The model utilized an orthotropic representation of the composite and contact between the washer and composite, bolt shank and composite, and the composite to rigid ground boundary.

Figure 4. Failure Test Solid Model, Global Shell FEM, and Refined Solid FEM

COMPARISON OF PREDICTIONS TO EXPERIMENTAL RESULTS

The events sequenced in Table 1 can be separated into three categories; incidents that can be quantitatively assessed, occurrences that can qualitatively evaluated, and those that did not occur. Table 2 displays the four predicted actions that can be quantified with the experiment's strain data and compares the load level at the event time with the predicted level. Gapping of the separation system, the first event, occurred close to the prediction, however, the composite failures transpired 32 to 37 percent past the forecasted load level. Not surprisingly, the explicitly realized actions did occur in the predicted order. Figures 5 through 10 detail the events described in Table 2.

Table 2. Failure Event Load Level Comparison

Demonstrated Level (% Limit Load)	Predicted Level (% Limit Load)	Event Description
232-268	253	Separation System Gapping
534	283	Access Door Doubler Bond Failure
792	600	Aft Joint Composite Compression
847	620	Open Hole Tension Failure at Aft Vent Hole

Figure 5. Separation System Joint Gap Data

Joint gapping of the separation system simulator was preceded by joint slip in the regions in line with the access door doublers because they created a stiff loadpath to transfer the global tension loads from the door area to ground. A change in slope of the strain gages on the door doubler meridian below the LLB at 232 percent of the flight load, shown in Figure 5, indicates the joint slipped and the tension load began to redistribute. As the load was increased the reading of two axially aligned gages on the aft cylindrical body, IM10691 and IM40691, diverged, signifying the interface gapped. The strain reduction in gages IM40691 and IR10691 at 268 percent further credit the gapping claim, as load was redirected away from the edges of the access doors to areas of the joint that were still in contact, reducing the strain in separated regions. This sequence straddled the predicted joint gap at 253 percent flight load. Slip was also visually observed after the test because the forward and aft extrusions edges at the motor assembly cut-out no longer aligned, an effect which could have been heightened by gapping.

Figure 6. Debonded Access Door Doubler

Debonding of the access door doubler occurred at nearly twice the predicted load level. The actual event was quite clear in both the strain gages near the door and the visual separation of the bond, shown in Figure 6. This grossly conservative discrepancy was partly due to less load passing through the bolts in the gapped area of the Lightband

during the test relative to the FEM, thus reducing the peak stresses in the bond which initiated failure. The bond ultimately failed as the tension load applied to the structure was increased causing the tension force passing through the LLB to eventually reach a point that caused failure in the bond. Another component of the disagreement was the conservatism in the model's presumed strength of the bonded interface. This approach is common in the aerospace industry standard finite element assumptions for bonds, which unfortunately restricts the use of bonded only joints.

Figure 7. Strain Shift Caused by Aft Joint Compression Failure

Figure 8. Compression Failure of the Aft Transition Radius

Aft joint region failure was predicted to be dominated by interlaminar stresses due to local bearing against the test tooling. The peak stress would occur at the maximum compression azimuth (270°) in the lower radius under 600 percent limit load. This failure mechanism would not cause an immediate catastrophic condition, but would allow the damaged region to accommodate additional loading until a significant area failed through the entire thickness. The damage would decrease the composite's stiffness, causing a non-linear structural response. After the onset of local failure, comprehensive loss of structural capacity is difficult to predict because the extent of damage and its effect on the overall performance of the test article is complicated to model. As evident in Figure 7, actual failure initiated at 792 percent meaning the estimate was 37 percent conservative. The inconsistency is largely due to the difficulty of accurately modeling the contact boundary condition. Failure progressed azimuthally away from the peak stress location, as demonstrated in the left graph of Figure 9,

resulting in significant damage through the thickness of the laminate from the 235° to 315° vent holes, shown in Figure 8. As predicted CASPAR continued to accommodate additional loading by redistributing load away from 270° azimuth, however, joint compression was not the ultimate cause of structural failure.

Figure 9. Strain Response of the Catastrophic Vent Hole Tension Failure

Unlike the joint compression failure propagation, the open hole tension mechanism caused sudden material damage in the through-thickness direction, shown in Figure 10, that instantaneously caused total structural failure. The strain data in the right side of Figure 9 demonstrates nearly all the gages near the 315° vent hole retreated to zero simultaneously. In fact, the entire structure lost the ability to withstand applied load at 847 percent of flight load, and the test was aborted.

Figure 10. Open Hole Tension Failures of the Compressed Vent Openings

Table 3. Qualitatively Assessed Failure Events

Qualitative Failure Assessment	Predicted Level (% Limit Load)	Event Description
NA	370	Sep System Bolt Yielding in-line with Access Door
Visual	400	Separation System Extrusion Yielding
Visual	465	Aft Joint Composite Tension
Post failure	646	Open Hole Compression Failure at Aft Vent Hole
Post failure	846	Shell Buckling

Table 3 lists the remaining predicted events that were either unable to be captured by test data or simply never happened. The first condition, yielding of the separation system bolts, never occurred despite being forecasted to happen at roughly 40 percent of

the ultimately applied load. This arose because the FEM did not represent the as-tested configuration. To prevent yielding of the bolts, the stainless steel fasteners were replaced with Grade 8.8 socket head cap screws in the critical tension regions of the Lightband. The FEM assumptions also included zero preload in the joint which led to unrealistic bending stresses in FEM bolts. This combination of alterations prevented bolt yielding from occurring during the failure test.

A post-test inspection found the radial pin holes in the Lightband morphed to an egg shape supporting the calculation that the separation system would yield; this event, however, had no bearing on the failure of CASPAR. It is important to reiterate that the LLB extrusions were joined to the composite shells via a bonded only joint, which is a large departure from standard practice in the space structure industry. Bonded joints typically contain redundant mechanical fasteners since only the edge of a bond and not the full interface can be inspected. Engineers fear the bond will not cover the entire intended area thus reducing the strength of the joint. Conversely, it is not problematic to inspect every bolt in a bolted joint, making them conservatively popular at a mass penalty to the structural system. It is worth noting this joint withstood nearly 8.5 times the compressive and 3 times the tensile flight loads with no indication of damage.

Visual examination after the failure test found composite skin wrinkling on the internal surface of the aft transitional radius, shown in Figure 11. This is evidence that the tensile force on the structure caused interlaminar normal failure in the radius. This event was not captured by data and is not believed to have had a significant effect on the failure of the structure.

Figure 11. Skin Wrinkling Caused by Tension of the CASPAR Shell

The final two events, open hole compression and shell buckling, were never given the opportunity of completion because they are mechanisms that naturally occur after the ultimate failure mode, open hole tension, in this configuration. Given the sequence of events, had open hole tension progressed more elegantly and had not caused sudden failure, open hole compression probably would have initiated at approximately 882 percent load. In that instance, open hole compression most likely would not have caused instantaneous failure either but the concurrent damage propagation caused by aft joint compression, open hole tension, and open hole compression in such close quarters

to one another would have quickly degraded the structural capability of CASPAR and led to ultimate failure long before shell buckling would have occurred in the test article.

CONCLUSION

The Air Force Research Laboratory conducted structural failure static tests on previously qualified, large space composite structures to quantitatively demonstrate the ultimate structural capability of the components, to compare the values to the flight conditions, and to analytically generated failure predictions. In this paper, the experimental results for CASPAR, a dual payload adapter and the program's first test article, were compared to failure predictions created with aerospace industry standard finite element analyses. A test design that caused a relevant composite failure while observing the limitations of remaining configuration and test system was challenging but successfully accomplished in this experiment. The finite element predictions were produced by utilizing FEMAP pre/post-processor and the NASTRAN solver. This process is extremely labor intensive but accurately forecasted the order of a series of events. The accuracy of the actual test load levels for predicted events varied greatly; however, the most crucial conditions were forecasted to occur approximately 35 percent earlier than realized. Although the predictions were conservative, they represent the margin of error commonly used to model composites, a margin that stifles optimal use of these materials. Additionally, even though this approach was rather straight forward, the process required an extensive background in both composite structural modelling and FEA boundary condition manipulation, practices that are more art than science, to yield only modest results.

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